

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE ASSESSMENT OF SOUTH SUDANESE REFUGEES IN ETHIOPIA TOWARDS TRADITIONAL MEDICINE: A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 04/02/2020

Available online

30/05/2020

Keywords

Traditional Medicine,
Attitude,
Knowledge,
Practice,
Refugees.

ABSTRACT

Practice of traditional medicine varies greatly from country to country, and the variation is seriously influenced by refugees. Refugees are facing significant barriers in accessing healthcare services. This study assessed knowledge, attitude and practice of south Sudanese refugees in Ethiopia towards traditional medicine. A community based cross-sectional study design was conducted on total of 151 randomly selected household from south Sudanese refugees in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. Structured interviewer administered questionnaire was used to collect data. Chi square test was used to determine association between variables. From the total of 151 participants, 84 (55.6%) were males. About 141 (96.7%) of the respondents know traditional medicine, and 120 (79.5%) of the respondents think as there were diseases which were not cured by modern medicine. Thus, 102 (67.5%) of respondents encourage others to use traditional medicine. Gender ($p=0.020$), duration of stay ($p=0.008$), marital status ($p=0.000$), family size ($p=0.041$), occupational status ($p=0.000$), and educational status ($p=0.000$) were significantly associated with practice of traditional medicine among refugees which lost their home. In conclusion, majority of respondents know traditional medicine especially, herbal type and use it because of their belief that herbals are natural thus encourage others practices. Moreover, practice of traditional medicine was significantly associated gender, duration of stay, marital status, family size, occupational status and educational status. Further study on standardization of herbal medicine is paramount to ensure its safety.

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Please cite this article in press as **Francis Majok and Gemmechu H.** Knowledge, Attitude and Practice Assessment of South Sudanese Refugees in Ethiopia Towards Traditional Medicine: A Cross Sectional Study. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2020:10(05).

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INTRODUCTION

World health organization (WHO) defines traditional medicine (TM) as health practices, approaches, knowledge's and believes incorporating plant, animal and mineral based medicine, spiritual, manual techniques and exercises, applied singularly or in combination to treat, diagnose and prevent illness and maintain well-being [1]. It is widely accepted and used in prevention and treatments of physical and mental disorder due to its intrinsic qualities, unique and holistic approaches as well as its accessibility [2]. According to the World Health Organization up to 80% of persons living in Africa, use traditional medicines for their primary healthcare needs [3]. The demand has been increasing as a result of growth of human population, shortage and unaffordable prices of modern drugs, and economic challenges associated with non-communicable diseases and the socio-cultural outlook of many patients in developing countries [4, 5]. However, practice of traditional medicine varies greatly from country to country and from region to region, as they are influenced by factors such as culture, history, personal attitude and philosophy [6, 7]. Moreover, different factors can lead to changes of knowledge, attitude and practice of traditional medicines in modern society like; globalization, migration from villages to cities, and cultural changes [8]. The situation is severe in case of refugees, who fled from their residences. Refugees face significant barriers in accessing and engaging with healthcare services [9]. In Sudan, more than three million people have been forced to flee their homes since the conflict began in December 2013. The ongoing conflict in south Sudan has generated nearly 1.9 million internally displaced persons (IDPS) in 2016/17 (50% of which estimated to be children), it has created food insecurity and lack of proper shelter and non-food items (NFI), and it has hindered the access to proper education and healthcare [10]. As a result, many South Sudan have fled to many foreign countries, and thus it hypothesized their knowledge, attitude and practice of traditional medicine may change in one way or other. To the best of author's knowledge, there is no data of association between refugees and knowledge, attitude and practice towards traditional medicine. This study assessed knowledge, attitude and practice of south Sudanese community, refugee in Ethiopia towards traditional medicine. Thus, the study will identify gaps in knowledge, attitude and practice of traditional medicine among south Sudanese in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. It is also a base line to concerned bodies, for instance the government of south Sudan especially the embassy of republic of south Sudan in Addis Ababa to undertake the intervention on the use of traditional medicine, formulate policies on traditional medicine, to do further investigations and to help improve lifestyle of people.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data was taken from the community based cross-sectional study conducted in south Sudanese refugees in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia from 1 April to 28 April, 2019 to assess knowledge, attitude and practice of south Sudanese community, refugee in Ethiopia towards traditional medicine. Addis Ababa is the capital city of Ethiopia. It is the largest city in the country, with a total population of 3,384,569 according to the 2007 census. Foreigners as well as many other African countries including south Sudanese reside in Addis Ababa; Ethiopia. Jimma University Institutional Review Board approved the research. We received a letter of permission from the ambassador in south Sudan embassy in Addis Ababa. To collect data, we obtained written informed consent of the study participants prior to interviews. The right of participants to withdraw from an interview at any time was maintained. We determined sample size using single population proportion formula. We studied all south Sudanese community resident in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia who fulfilled the inclusion criteria and found in the place during the study period. We translated an English version of the questionnaire to local language and back translated to English. The data collection tool was also pretested. We included individual populations from the age of 18years and above and have given full consent. Participants with hearing problems and who have not given consent were excluded from the study. Data were collected by four trained pharmacists. A structured interviewer administered questionnaire was used to collect data on knowledge, attitude, practice and socio-demographic characteristics.

Statistical analysis

Each questionnaire was checked for completeness and accuracy before entering the data into SPSS. The data was cleaned for errors and missing data, coded, categorized and sorted to facilitate the analysis and entered into the computer. We analyzed the data using SPSS Version 21.0 (Chicago, SPSS Inc.). We used Chi square tests to determine association between categorical variables and practice of traditional medicine. The results were summarized using percentages, bar charts, in text, tables and graphs. Moreover, the Chi square test was to determine association between practice of traditional medicine among refugees and socio-demographic characteristics.

Results

Socio-demographic characteristics of study subject

From a total of 151 participants who were identified for the study, all of them participated in the study, yielding the response rate of 100%. Eighty four (55.6%) of 151 of the respondents were males while 67(44.4%) were females and majority of was found in the age group of 29- 39 (39.1%). Catholic took the highest religions group (41.1%), followed by protestant (40.4%) and the least was orthodox (0.7%) [Table 1].

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of study participants.

Variables		Frequency	Percentages (%)
Sex	Male	84	55.6
	Female	67	44.4
Age	18-28	50	33.1
	29-39	59	39.1
	40-50	22	14.6
	51-61	6	4.0
	>=62	14	9.3
Region	Orthodox	1	0.7
	Catholic	62	41.1
	Protestant	61	40.4
	Muslim	7	4.6
	Others	20	13.2
How long have you lived in the area?	1-2 years	63	41.7
	3-4 years	72	47.7
	>5 years	16	10.6
Marital status	Single	64	42.4
	Married	72	47.7
	Widowed	12	7.9
	Divorced	3	2.0
	Others	20	13.2
No. Of household occupants	1-2	28	18.5
	3-4	53	35.1
	5-6	47	31.1
	>6	22	14.6
Occupation(work status)	Government employee	38	25.2
	Unemployed & with no regular income	54	35.8
	Self-employed (trade, farmer, artist etc.)	30	19.9
	Retired	4	2.6
	Others(student)	25	16.6
Education status	None	33	21.9
	Primary	22	14.6
	Secondary	31	20.5
	Higher education	65	43.0
Average income in birr per month of the household	<500	29	19.2
	500 to 1500	78	51.7
	>1500	44	29.1

Knowledge of the study subjects towards traditional medicine

One hundred and forty six (96.7%) of the respondents answered that they have heard about traditional medicine. For true or false questions, 28(18.5%) of respondents answered correct answer for questions entitled as, there is no harmful traditional medicine. However, 142(94.0%), 64(42.4%) of respondents have answered correct answer for question entitled as Health education about risks and benefits of traditional medicine is important and Traditional medicine are more effective and safer than modern health services respectively [Table 2]. Majority of respondents 39.70% stated side effect of traditional medicine like skin rash, vomiting and dizziness, and 29% know diarrhea as side effect of traditional medicine [Figure 1].

Table 2: Knowledge of respondents towards traditional medicine.

Characteristics		Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Have you ever heard of tm?	Yes	146	96.7
	No	5	3.3
There is no harmful traditional medicine	True	28	18.5
	False	123	81.5
Health education about risks and benefits of traditional medicine is important	True	142	94.0
	False	9	6.0
Traditional medicine are more effective and safer than modern health services	True	64	42.4
	False	87	57.6

Figure 1: Known adverse effects of traditional medicine of the respondents.

Attitudes study subjects towards traditional medicine

About 57 (37.7%) of respondents prefer traditional medicine for treatment of their diseases. Twenty nine (52.7%) of respondents prefer TM because of affordability. Forty nine (32.5%) of the respondents did not encourage others to use traditional medicine and 102(67.5%) did encourage others to use traditional medicine because of cost 55(36.4%), availability 41(27.2%), religion 7(4.6%) and others 1(0.7%). One hundred twenty (79.5%) of the respondents believe that there are disease that are not cured by modern medicine and 31(20.5%) think that there are no disease. One hundred and twelve (74.2%) of the respondents agree that traditional medicine should be documented and evaluated through research for their safety, efficacy and quality; 18 (11.9%) don't agree and 21(13.9%) had no idea. 91 (60.3%) of them had interest to document traditional medicine knowledge that they know or get from elder person or other sources while 56 (37.1%) didn't have interest [Table 3].

Table 3: Attitude of respondents towards traditional medicine.

Characteristics		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Which do you prefer?	Traditional medicine	57	37.7
	Modern medicine	94	62.3
If your response is traditional medicine, please explain why prefer it?	More effective than modern medicine	11	20.0
	More accessible than modern medicine	15	27.3
	More affordable than modern medicine	29	52.7
If your response is modern medicine, why?	More effective and safer than traditional medicine	69	70.4
	Modern medicine is validated through research	29	29.6
Do you encourage others to use tm?	Yes	102	67.5
	No	49	32.5
Why do you encourage others to use tm?	Religion	7	6.7
	Cost	55	52.9
	Availability	41	39.4
	Others	1	1.0
Do you think that there are diseases not cured by modern medicine?	Yes	120	79.5
	No	31	20.5
Do you agree that traditional remedies should be documented and evaluated through research for their safety, efficacy and quality?	Yes	112	74.2
	No	18	11.9
	I have no idea	21	13.9
If yes, do you have the interest to document traditional medicine knowledge that you know or get from elder person or other sources?	Yes	91	61.9
	No	56	38.1

Practice of the study subjects on traditional medicine

Ninety (59.6%) of the respondents have used traditional medicine after their exile, and the rest 61(40.4%) did not use traditional medicine. Among the respondents who have used the different forms of traditional medicine; 101(66.9%) of the respondents mentioned that the outcome was improved. While 37(24.5%) of them complained that the outcome was partially improved and 13(8.6%) had no change. From the total of household owners who participated in the study, 135 (89.4%) have shown interest to cooperate with traditional healers, modern medicine health workers and researchers [Table 4].

Table 4: Practice of study participants towards traditional medicine.

Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percentages (%)	
Have you ever used traditional medicine for self-medication after flee	Yes No	90 61	59.6 40.4
What are the main sources of supply of herbal products?	From practitioner Relatives Neighbors Friends Themselves	53 61 15 10 9	35.8 41.2 10.1 6.8 6.1
What do you usually do first when you or your family members fall ill in the last one year?	Home remedies Modern medicine Both traditional medicine and modern medicine serially Visited traditional healer Visited modern health care services Visited both traditional healer and modern medicine serially or concurrently	37 50 26 3 34 1	24.5 33.1 17.2 2.0 22.5 0.7
For which illness do you prefer to visit or take your family member to a modern health facility?	Illnesses that require surgery Very serious illnesses Almost all illnesses	8 1 142	5.3 0.7 94.0
For which illness do you prefer to visit or take your family member to a traditional healer?	Evil spirit, mental problems and broken bones Illnesses non-responsive to modern medicine Others e.g. cancers, hemorrhoids	97 22 32	64.2 14.6 21.2
If you or any family member has been treated by traditional healer over the last one or more years, was the health condition restored or improved from illness?	Cured/improved from illness Partially improved Not cured or improved from illness	101 37 13	66.9 24.5 8.6
Do you support the cooperation among traditional healers, modern medicine health workers and researchers?	Yes No	135 16	89.4 10.6
If yes, in what way do you suggest cooperation between traditional healers, modern medicine health workers and researchers?	Information and experience sharing on knowledge for each other Patients referral when the health condition is not improved with traditional medicine treatment Giving opportunity to play role in advice and counseling of patients in disease prevention and control by healers Others	59 71 5 1	43.4 52.2 3.7 0.7
If your response is no, could you please state possible reasons for no need for cooperation?	I do not believe in traditional medicine Difference in principles and lack of agreement between the two discipline Traditional healers keep their knowledge about traditional medicine secret	3 12 1	18.8 75.0 6.3

Factors Associated with practice of Traditional medicine

We used Chi square tests to determine association between categorical variables and practice of traditional medicine. The study revealed that, gender ($p=0.020$), duration of stay ($p=0.008$), marital status ($p=0.000$), number of house hold ($p=0.041$), occupational status ($p=0.000$), and education status ($p=0.000$) were significantly associated with practice of traditional medicine among refugees which lost their home [Table 5].

Table 5: Association between Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents and practice of Traditional medicine after exile.

Variables		Frequency	Practice of TM after exile		Chi Square	p-value
			Yes	No		
Gender	Male	84	43	41	5.564	0.020*
	Female	67	47	20		
Age	18-28	50	32	18	1.145	0.886
	29-39	59	33	26		
	40-50	22	14	8		
	51-61	6	3	3		
	>/=62	14	8	6		
Duration of stay	1-2 years	63	29	34	9.656	0.008*
	3-4 years	72	52	20		
	>5 years	16	9	7		
Marital status	Single	64	23	41	26.181	0.000*
	Married	72	55	17		
	Widowed	12	10	2		
	Divorced	3	2	1		
No. Of household occupants	1-2	28	18	10	8.258	0.041*
	3-4	53	34	19		
	5-6	48	31	17		
	>6	22	7	15		
Occupation(work status)	Government employee	38	23	15	23.961	0.000*
	Unemployed & with no regular income	54	34	20		
	Self-employed (trade, farmer, artist etc.)	38	25	5		
	Retired	54	3	1		
	Others(student)	25	5	20		
Educational status	None	33	31	2	23.972	0.000*
	Primary	22	14	8		
	Secondary	31	17	14		
	Higher education	65	28	37		
Average income in birr per month of the household	<500	29	15	14	3.346	0.188
	500 to 1500	78	52	26		
	>1500	29	23	21		

Significant***Traditional medicinal practice used by respondents**

Common medicinal plants used for the treatment of human diseases: local name, scientific name, disease treated, part(s) used, method of preparation were depicted in Table 6.

Table 6: medicinal plant used for the treatment of human diseases: local name, scientific name, disease treated, part(s) used, method of preparation.

S/N	Local name	Scientific name	Illness types	Part(s) used	Methods of preparation
1	Neem	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> a.juss. And <i>melia azadirachta</i> l.	Used as poultice and applied for treatment of <i>abudiqnandayira</i> (mumps). Frayed twigs are used as toothbrushes. Also used in treating skin infections and diseases including eczema, measles, chicken pox, malaria and swellings (<i>dabas</i>), as insect repellent, anti-lice, and repellent of worms when taking on an empty stomach.	Stem, bark, and leaves	Boiled and drank
2.	Tiet(dinka,nuer)	<i>Khaya senegalensis</i> (desr.) A.juss.	Used in treating malaria, liver affections, abdominal disorders, and sinusitis. Leaves are used to treat skin affections, abdominal disorders, and trachoma.	Bark	Macerate of bark
3.	Ginger	<i>Zingiber officinalis</i> rosc. And <i>amomumzingiber</i>	The rhizome is used as beverage, in treating joints affections, common cold, chest complaints, heartburn, and as anti-cough.	Rhizome	Beverage
4	Porsho(mandari)	<i>Ziziphusspp.</i>	Used in treating diarrhea.	Tuberous root (eaten)	Eaten(chewed)
5	Kirot(mandari)	<i>Combretumfragransf</i>	Used in treating leprosy and jaundice. Root is used in fumigation "to cleanse a dead person's possessions".	Bark	Boiled and drank
6	Lulu and rak(dinka)	<i>Butyrospermumparkii.</i>	Massaged for relief of sciatica pain. Used in treating sciatica, for food and as oil source.	Oil	Fried, grounded and cooked to separate oil
7	Gum arabia	<i>Caciasenegal</i>	Its gum is used in treating peptic ulcer, diarrhea, and in water purification. Recently it is alleged to help patients with end-stage renal failure.	Gum	Chewed
8	Chiey(ardeb)(nuer)	<i>Tamarindus indica.</i>	Treat malaria and jaundice	Fruits	Infusion of fruits senna, qurunful, and karkade added is drunk
10	Akiol(dinka)	<i>Salvadorapersica.</i>	Used in treating <i>dabas</i> , flatulence, colic, as anthelmintic, toothbrush. Juice is used to aid digestion, and as contraceptive.	Root; fruits; stem; bark	Macerate of the bark
11	Tu (shulluk)	<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i>	Seven (7) unripe fruits sucked to induce abortion, and the plant is used in contraception. Plant could be laxative, anti-bilharzias, emetic, anti-diabetic, and detergent.	Fruits and leaves	Sucked and macerated for laxative, emetic

DISCUSSION

According to the results of this study, the proportion of male (55.6%) in the sample was higher when compared to the female (44.4%). This is somewhat expected due to the head of family is the husband and at the time of interview house wives give chance for husband. Of the total respondents, the majority 72(47.7%) were married and majority was found in the age group of 29-39(39.1%), this coincides with the results of study done on people of Burka Jato the sex ratio was predominated by male (63%) and the majority was found in the age group of 30-39 (31.56%); more than half of the Burka Jato people (56%) were married [11]

This study indicates that 14.6% of the respondent were primary school, 20.5% secondary school, 43% were higher education and the rest 21.9% were uneducated; this sharply agrees with the study result of the study done in northern Ethiopia reported that 46.9% of the respondents had attend tertiary education, 2.8% had only primary education and the rests are non-educated [12]. In this study, 49 (32.5%) of the respondents did not encourage others to use traditional medicine and 102(67.5%) did encourage others to use traditional medicine because of cost 55(36.4%), availability 41(27.2%), religion 7(4.6%) and others 1(0.7%). One hundred twenty (79.5%) of the respondents believe that there are diseases that are not cured by modern medicine and 31(20.5%) think that there are no diseases not cared by modern medicine. This enormously differ from the findings of a study conducted in Jara town, bale zone south east Ethiopia in which one hundred seventy four (64.2%) of the respondents were not encourage others to use traditional medicine and 97(35.8%) were encourage others to use traditional medicine because of religion 19(19.58%), cost 19(19.58%), availability 47(48.45%) and others 12(12.37%).

One hundred forty eight (54.61%) of the respondents believe that there are disease that are not cured by modern medicine and 123(45.38%) think that there are no diseases not cured by modern medicine [11]. This discrepancy could be attributed to fact that many south Sudanese liked the practice of tm with culture and religion, secondly the low economic income could contribute as, many people are unemployed and living in refugee's camp. The ailments most commonly managed by the respondents were malaria (20.1%), GIT problems (19.5%), and diarrhea (10.4%) among others. This is comparable to the research reported in bench ethnic group (south west Ethiopia) by Gidayet *al.*, about 14% of the respondents used TM for the treatment of GIT problems [13].

The percentage of respondents who practiced TM in the last 2 years was, 96.7%; common types of tm known to the community were herbal medicine 56(36.8%), bone setting 9(5.9%) and TBA 2(1.3%) which correlates to the research among Burka Jato people whereby 94.22% had practiced TM at least in the last 2 years and the remaining 5.78% did not practice TM; type of TM used; medicinal herbs 70.57%, bone setting 16%, animal or mineral product 11.43% and spiritual faith healing 2%. (28). About 37.7% of the respondents preferred TM to modern medicine which is similar to the research reported by Elujobaet *al.* About 35.7% prefer TM [14]. The reasons for preference of TM might be due to its; affordability (52.5%), accessible (27.3%) and effectiveness (20.0%). This is similar to the research conducted in Nigeria; cheap (21.4%), accessible (16.4%) and acceptable (13.4%) [15].

About 60.2% of the respondents were aware of the adverse effects from TM and these include diarrhea (26.5%), skin rash, vomiting, dizziness (29.1%) and others(4.6%), which is similar to the research conducted in Wayu town, western Ethiopia in which more than half of the respondents, 184 (60.79%), were aware of the major side effects of complementary and alternative medicine, such as diarrhea (111, 36.64%), vomiting (62, 20.5%), abdominal pain (45, 14.91%), and the remaining (84, 27.95%) were not aware of the side effects of complementary and alternative medicine [16].

Moreover, the study revealed that, gender ($p=0.020$), duration of stay ($p=0.008$), marital status ($p=0.000$), number of house hold ($p=0.041$), occupational status ($p=0.000$) and education status ($p=0.000$) were significantly associated with practice of traditional medicine among refugees which lost their home. This result similar with study conducted in among the Communities of Merawi Town, Northwest Ethiopia even though family size, annual income, and marital status were found to have no association with use of traditional medicine [17] which is against the current finding. This might be due to study population differences. In this study the populations were drawn from communities of refugees in which barriers in accessing and engaging with healthcare services was resorted.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes most of our respondents know traditional medicine especially herbal type and use it because of their belief that herbals are natural and the majority of them encourage others to use traditional medicine because of its affordability. Moreover, gender, duration of stay, marital status, number of house hold, occupational status and education status were significantly associated with practice of traditional medicine among refugees which lost their home. Further study on standardization of herbal medicine is paramount to ensure its safety.

ABBREVIATIONS

CAM	: Complementary and Alternative medicine
CBE	: Community Based Education
IDPS	: Internally Displaced persons
MM	: Modern Medicine
NFI	: Non-Food Items
NHIS	: National Health Insurance Scheme.
TM	: Traditional Medicine
TCAM	: Traditional, Complementary and Alternative medicine
WHO	: World Health Organization

Declaration

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Authors' Contributions

GH and FM designed, extracted, analyzed and interpreted the data. GH conceived the study; guided the design and supervised the whole research. GH also prepared the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was support by Jimma University. We would like to acknowledge all study participants, South Sudan especially the embassy of republic of South Sudan in Addis Ababa for their kind cooperation during the data collection period.

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